

Review Proposal: Does appropriate social care provision impact the length of stay and clinical outcomes of patients who are medically ready for discharge in the UK?: A scoping review.

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Review Title and Basic Details:

Review Title: Does appropriate social care provision impact the length of stay and clinical outcomes of patients who are medically ready for discharge in the UK?: A scoping review.

Condition or Domain being studied: Interaction of social care and hospital inpatient care.

Rationale for the Review: In September 2025, more than 12,000 patients in hospitals in England no longer met the 'criteria to reside' but were not able to be discharged (NHS England, 2025). There are many potential reasons for this delay in patient discharge, but one that is often proposed is a lack of appropriate social care provision. Delayed discharge can have a significant impact on patient outcomes, increasing the risk of hospital acquired infections, and deconditioning (Chen, et al., 2022). Thus, it can also contribute to higher rates of hospital readmission and patient mortality. However, it is unclear what information is available in the literature measuring the interaction between timely and appropriate social care and hospital length of stay and discharge outcomes. A scoping review will systematically map the existing research and identify any gaps.

Review Objectives: To determine whether improving social care services will have an impact on hospital discharge and post-hospital patient outcomes.

Keywords: Bed blocking, social care, Delayed hospital discharge, medically fit for discharge

Country: UK

Eligibility Criteria

Population: Adults who are medically optimised for discharge, who are inpatients in hospitals.

Exclude articles that focus on children or neonates or that focus on adults who are not medically optimised for discharge.

Concept: Appropriate social care provision.

Context: Hospitals in the UK

Exclusion Criteria: Opinion pieces, viewpoints, review protocols, conceptual frameworks, conference abstracts, commentaries, and conference proceedings will be excluded from this paper. All non-health papers will be excluded from this review.

Searching and screening

Search for unpublished studies: Yes.

Main bibliographic databases that will be searched: Medline, CINAHL plus, Embase, ASSIA

Search Language Restrictions: English

Search Date Restrictions: N/A

Other methods of identifying studies: Hand searching.

Search strategy:

	Search Terms used (Title/abstract)
Social care	Social care Domiciliary care Social worker Home care Residential care
Delayed discharge	delayed transfer of care delayed discharge bed blocking exit block fit for discharge medically optimised
Downstream effect	rehospitalisation readmission mortality all-cause mortality at home mortality excess mortality mortality mortality rate mortality risk mortality risk score nursing home mortality out-of-hospital mortality standardized mortality ratio hospital readmission hospitalization
In the UK	United Kingdom UK Scotland Wales Northern Ireland Great Britain NHS National Health Service

Data Collection Process

Data extraction from published articles and reports:

- Author(s)
- Year of publication
- Geographical region
- Aims/purpose.
- Population and sample size.
- Methodology/methods
- Intervention type/duration, comparator
- Outcome measures

These elements from each study that meets the criteria will be entered into a table.

Study risk of bias or quality assessment: Critical appraisal will be undertaken using the relevant CASP checklist.

Outcomes to be analysed.

Main Outcomes:

- 1) Length of stay in hospital post medical optimisation.
- 2) Downstream effect of appropriate social care:
 - a) Rehospitalisation within 30 or 180 days
 - b) Mortality within 180 days

Sub analyses:

- 1) What social care interventions improve delay.
- 2) Stratify by reason for hospital admission.

Planned data synthesis.

The data will be synthesised using a narrative synthesis approach based on guidance by Popay et al. (2006)

1. Preliminary synthesis which will discuss elements such as:
 - a. Types of study found- It would be important to highlight what studies are most represented. It will also be important to discuss if there are types of studies that are not represented and understand if that is due to feasibility reasons or for another reason.
 - b. Common reasons for exclusion of studies from the results
 - c. Results of quality assessment – Highlight any very high-quality studies in description.
 - d. Whether they used quantitative or qualitative methods
2. Exploring relationships within and between studies:
 - a. Differences in the direction of effect
 - b. Differences in the size of the effect
 - c. Possible reasons for these differences
3. Assessing the robustness of the synthesis

Review Affiliation, Funding and Peer Review

Review Team Members: Prisha Goel

Review Affiliation: Brighton and Sussex Medical School

Funding source: N/A

Additional Information

Review conflict of interest: None Known

Country: UK

References

Chen, Y., Almirall-Sánchez, A. & Domínguez-Vive, C., 2022. Hospital-associated deconditioning: Not only physical, but also cognitive. *International Journal of Geriatric Psychiatry*.

NHS England, 2025. *Acute discharge situation report*. [Online]

Available at: <https://www.england.nhs.uk/statistics/statistical-work-areas/discharge-delays/acute-discharge-situation-report/>

[Accessed 8 November 2025].

Popay, J. et al., 2006. *Guidance on the conduct of narrative synthesis in systematic reviews: A product from the ESRC Methods Programme*. s.l.:Lancaster University.